

Analytical Applications of 2'-Hydroxy-4-Methoxy-5'-Methyl Chalcone Oxime (HMMCO : Gravimetric Determination of Palladium(II), Copper(II) and Nickel(II)

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2'-Hydroxy-4-methoxy-5'-methyl chalcone oxime (HMMCO) has been found to be wide spectrum precipitant for a number of transition metal ions. It gives a orange red bis-chelate with Pd(II) pH (0.5-1.0), a buff coloured bis-chelate with Cu(II) pH (3.0-3.5) and a light green bis-chelate with Ni(II) pH (7.2-9.2). The bis-chelates are granular, stable and are quantitatively formed. Pd(II) has been determined alone in 0.1N HCl medium at various concentrations and some experiments have been carried out to determine Pd(II), Cu(II) and Ni(II) in their ternary mixture.

2'-HYDROXY-4-methoxy-5'-methyl chalcone oxime (HMMCO) has the system

$$\begin{array}{c} | \\ \text{C-OH} \\ || \quad \diagup \text{NOH} \\ \text{C-C-C} = \text{C-} \\ | \quad | \end{array}$$

similar to many precipitating agents. The investigations of reagents having system

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{OH} \\ | \\ \text{-C} = \text{C-C} = \text{NOH} \\ | \end{array}$$

have been undertaken by several workers¹⁻⁵. The studies on salicylaldehyde^{2,3,6}, resacetophenone oxime^{7,8} and *o*-hydroxy acetophenone oxime⁹ lead to the conclusion that the precipitation is a function of pH and characteristic of the reagent.

The HMMCO being a large molecule, the small amount of Pd(II) upto 2 mg can be estimated quantitatively. Low conversion factors, i.e., 0.1586, 0.1012 and 0.0942 for Pd(II), Cu(II) and Ni(II) respectively indicate that very less amount of metal ions can be determined quantitatively. Next, the complexes being insoluble in 60% ethanol the excess of reagent which gets precipitated along the complex is easily washed out. Pd(II) can be estimated in presence of large number of interfering ions. The gravimetric determination of Pd(II), Cu(II) and Ni(II) have been carried out with satisfactory results taking advantage of the pH range for the precipitation.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of B.D.H. and A.R. grade. Stock solutions of metal ions were prepared by dissolving pure salts in double distilled water and

were employed after standardisation by standard methods¹². The pH of the solution was adjusted to desired values by using hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide for Pd(II), acetic acid and ammonium hydroxide for Cu(II) and borax-boric acid buffer for Ni(II). G₄-sintered glass crucible (JENA) was used for all gravimetric estimations. ELICO pH meter with glass and saturated calomel electrodes was used to measure the pH of the solutions.

Reagent : 2'-Hydroxy-4-methoxy-5'-methyl chalcone oxime¹⁰ (HMMCO) : The 2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone obtained by Fries migration of *p*-cresylacetate was treated with anisaldehyde and sodium hydroxide in ethanol; the product was decomposed with hydrochloric acid to get 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5'-methyl chalcone. The HMMCO was prepared from this chalcone by its reaction with hydroxylamine hydrochloride. It was purified by crystallization from ethanol to get the m.p. 85°. One per cent solution of HMMCO in ethanol was used as reagent. (Found : C, 72.10; H, 6.02; N, 4.86% and calcd. for C₁₇H₁₇O₃N : C, 72.07; H, 6.00; N, 4.95%).

Determination of Palladium(II) : A solution of Pd(II) containing a known amount of metal ions was taken in a clean and dry 400 ml pyrex glass beaker, diluted to 50 ml and treated with a calculated amount of hydrochloric acid to yield a final concentration of 0.1N. Precipitation was carried out in cold by adding a slight excess of reagent solution dropwise with constant stirring. Then the beaker was kept at room temperature for half an hour. The orange red precipitate was filtered through a previously weighed sintered crucible. The precipitate was washed first with hot water and then with 60% alcohol till free from reagent (the reagent itself yields a green colour with freshly prepared $\frac{1}{2}$ FeCl₃

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solution). The precipitate was dried to constant weight at 110° and weighed as Pd(C₁₇H₁₆O₃N)₂. It has been found that Pd(II) can be quantitatively estimated in the pH range 0.5–1.0. Conversion factor for Pd(II) is 0.1586. Typical results obtained with Pd(II) are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF Pd(II) AT pH 0.5–1.0

Serial No.	Wt. of Pd(II) taken in mg.	Wt. of Pd(II)-Oximate in mg.	Wt. of Pd(II) found in mg.	Error	
				in mg.	in %
1	2.27	14.00	2.22	-0.05	-2.20
2	4.54	28.20	4.47	-0.07	-1.54
3	6.81	43.48	6.90	+0.09	+1.32
4	9.09	57.61	9.14	+0.05	+0.55
5	11.36	71.42	11.32	-0.04	-0.35
6	18.18	114.8	18.21	+9.03	+0.16
7	22.72	143.4	22.74	+0.02	+0.09
8	31.81	201.1	31.89	+0.08	+0.25
9	45.45	285.9	45.34	-0.11	-0.24

Effect of diverse ions on gravimetric estimation of Pd(II): To study the effect of diverse ions on gravimetric estimation of Pd(II), 50 mg of various cations as well as anions were added to 11.36 mg of Pd(II) solution at pH 1.0 and estimation was carried out as mentioned above. The results obtained show that Cu⁺⁺, Ni⁺⁺, Ba⁺⁺, Mn⁺⁺, Cd⁺⁺, Co⁺⁺, Zn⁺⁺, Fe⁺⁺, Fe⁺⁺⁺, Al⁺⁺⁺, citrate, tartrate, nitrate, oxalate, phosphate, borate and chloride do not interfere in the analysis.

Estimation of Pd(II), Cu(II) and Ni(II) in their ternary mixture: An aliquot containing known amount of Pd(II), Cu(II) and Ni(II) was diluted to 150 ml and the pH was adjusted to 1.0. The precipitation of Pd(II) was carried out as described earlier. After removing the filtrate the precipitate was washed by 60% ethanol so as to remove the precipitated reagent, and Pd(II) was estimated as before.

The pH of the filtrate was made up to 3.5 by acetic acid and ammonium hydroxide. Further quantity of reagent solution was added slowly with constant stirring in slight excess. The buff coloured Cu(II)-oximate precipitated was digested at about 60°–70° for half an hour. Then it was filtered and washed as above and the precipitate was dried at 100° and weighed as Cu(C₁₇H₁₆O₃N)₂. The conversion factor for Cu(II) is 0.1012.

The filtrate after removal of copper(II)-oximate was warmed up to 60° and pH was raised to 9.0 by borax and boric acid. Ni(II) was precipitated by adding slight excess of the reagent with constant stirring.

The light green Ni(II)-oximate was digested at 60°–70° for half an hour, filtered, washed as in previous cases and dried at 110°. The precipitate was weighed as Ni(C₁₇H₁₆O₃N)₂. The conversion factor is 0.0942. The results are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF Pd(II), Cu(II) AND Ni(II) IN THEIR TERNARY MIXTURE

Metal ions	Wt. of metal ions taken in mg.	pH	Wt. of metal ions found in mg.	Error	
				in mg.	in %
Pd ²⁺	i) 11.36	1.0	11.31	-0.05	-0.44
	ii) 22.72		22.63	-0.09	-0.40
Cu ²⁺	i) 10.00	3.5	9.97	-0.03	-0.30
	ii) 20.00		19.95	-0.05	-0.25
Ni ²⁺	i) 10.00	9.0	9.97	-0.08	-0.80
	ii) 20.00		19.95	-0.12	-0.60

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